

Evaluation of some CMS and maintainer lines in Tamil Nadu

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Five new cytotsterile lines from IRRI were evaluated with check variety V20 A during 1987. Five plants in each CMS line were selected randomly to assess pollen stainability, spikelet fertility, plant height, tiller number per plant, days to 50% flowering, and panicle exsertion.

Pollen stainability was lowest in IR54753 A (0.1%) and highest in IR54752 A (10%) (see table). Spikelet fertility in bagged panicles was zero in all lines. Tillering was relatively low in IR54753 A (13 tillers) and highest in IR54757 A (41 tillers). IR54756 A and

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CMS or maintainer	Pollen stainability (%)	On bagged panicles	Spikelet fertility ^a (%) on open pollinated panicles	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Days (no.) to 50% flowering	Panicle exsertion (grade) ^b
IR54752 A/ IR54752 B	10.0	0	0.3	106 122	23 22	101 103	7 1
IR54753 A/ IR54753 B	0.1	0	0.8	103 115	13 19	101 105	7 1
IR54154 A/ IR54754 B	5.0	0	0.3	99 115	22 20	99 102	7 1
IR54756 A/ IR54756 B	0.4	0	0.8	85 97	31 27	89 92	7 1
IR54757 A/ IR54757 B	1.2	0	0.4	74 89	41 23	87 90	7 1
V20 A/ V20 B	0.5	0	4.12	65 70	35 28	65 67	7 1

^aValue is zero on bagged panicles. ^b1 = normal.

IR54757 A flowered early, but later than V20 A. The other lines had medium duration. Heading difference between A and B lines was 2-3 d in all lines tested.

Mild incidence of leaf spot was observed in IR54753 and IR54754.

Panicle exsertion was poor in all A lines and normal in B lines. □

Yield potential

Correlation between yield and its components in upland rice in Cuba

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During 1984 wet season, we studied six varieties in rainfed fields in Sancti Spiritus and Havana Provinces, to establish the correlations between grain yield and its components. Plots were laid out in random block design with four replications. Total rainfall during the experiment was 637 mm in Havana and 694 mm in Sancti Spiritus.

Panicles/m² had no relation to grain yield; 1,000-grain weight and filled

spikelets/panicle were highly related to grain yield (see figure).

These results are similar to those with the same varieties in irrigated fields. □

Analysis of rice panicle structure

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We studied the panicle structure from 10 primary tillers of 80 rice cultivars and lines for two seasons. Table 1 shows the panicle characters of some of the parents and their hybrids.

There were four distinct types of parents. The IR cultivars and Rewa type (PAU125-1-2/Lalco 14) have similar panicle structure. However, Rewa type has more spikelets on the secondary branches (SB) than do IR cultivars. Glaberrima type has more primary branches (PB) and spikelets on primary branches, with few SB and spikelets. The upland type derived from an anther-cultured Moroberekan/Palawan cross is intermediate. The upland type

Yield (t/ha)

Correlation between upland rice yield and its components in Cuba.